

Fostering Creativity and Expression in Handling Mapeh Subjects: Teachers Practices in Focus

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Abstract. This study aimed to explore the fostering of creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects wherein the teachers' practices focus MAPEH was one of the learning areas in the k to 12 curriculum, which has four components: music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health. The study comprised a unique group of ten (10) participants, all of whom were active public high school faculty members during the 2023-2024 academic year. The findings disclosed that the teachers' lived experience was shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression, and the three themes are adapting pedagogical approaches, holistic approaches, and diverse strategies. The MAPEH teachers manage creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development. The themes are Empowering Through Creative Engagement, Navigating Constraints to Foster Creative Empowerment, and Cultivating Creative Empowerment. Moreover, the educational management insight drawn from the study of how teachers handle creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development, and the three themes are guiding principles for creative pedagogy, policy recommendations for holistic curriculum integration, and empowering teachers as agents of change.

KEY WORDS

1. fostering creativity
2. expression in handling MAPEH subjects
3. teachers practices

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1. Introduction

Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) are essential subjects in a student's education because they help develop the whole person. MAPEH teachers play an essential role in promoting creativity and self-expression among students. This study aims to understand how MAPEH teachers perceive their responsibilities in encouraging these qualities and what challenges they face. The research utilized surveys, interviews, and observations to gather data from different educational settings. By understanding the perspectives of MAPEH teachers, educational policies can be improved to enhance the quality of instruction and create an environment where students can explore their creativity freely. Ultimately, this can lead to a more enriching educational experience for students that contributes to their overall development. MAPEH is one of the learning areas in the K to 12 Curriculum, which has four components, namely, Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health. It is a learning area that has a wider scope. Thus, there is a need for teachers to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to

provide effective instruction to students. However, it is sad to note that not all teachers have sufficient knowledge and skills to effectively deliver instructions. There are some who may be musically inclined, have skills and knowledge in the arts, have experience and knowledge in different sports, and may be knowledgeable in health. However, there are only a few who have the required skills in all these components, considering that the MAPEH curriculum is equally important with all the other learning areas (Malvin Quiles Dulay, 2022). Global context, Bassar (2019) opined that sports and physical education should be a positive and constructive force in the growth and development of every child. Adequate time should be allotted to the growth and development of boys and girls during school days and periods when the children are not in school. Supported by the study by Nordly Yanik, (2020). stresses the need for the improvement of professional preparation of physical education and sports teachers and a periodic and through a program of evaluation. He added that one of the real values of in-service growth is to meet the inadequacy of pre-service education for teachers. Likewise, he emphasized that every mentor must be adept in exercising his profession to promote the continuous improvement of his duties toward the school system's curriculum. In-service training. National context, The Department of Education recognizes the interest of students in the different disciplines such as in Arts, Science, Language, and Sports. In its thrust to produce globally competitive learners, special curricular programs in secondary schools were implemented to meet the needs and talents of the students (DO 46 s. 2020). Furthermore, the needs and interests of the learners should be the prime consideration when creating and designing a curriculum. Thus, the needs, talents, and interests of students play a vital role and should be considered in implementing special curricular programs, which are offered by the Department of Education in secondary schools (Hoyt-Oukada, 2023). The enhanced basic education curriculum supports special programs in science and technology, journalism, foreign language, technical-vocational education, arts, and sports (K12). The Deped, aside from basic education, should also promote special curricular programs, most especially the development of the sports program (Field, 2021). In the local context, there is a ban, where English teachers are assigned to teach MAPEH. Indeed, MAPEH, as a key learning area, is of significant significance in developing all learners in various grade levels in the Philippine Secondary Schools. MAPEH, in its four components, is designed to develop students holistically. In addition, the word holistically is too heavy to carry if the ones responsible for teaching the latter are out-of-field and do not have enough knowledge and training to execute all its components (Silvestre, 2020). In the Philippines, under the K to 12 Curriculum, the Physical Education program seeks to provide opportunities for the physical development of Filipino learners through the development of various competencies under the basic education curriculum by providing appropriate activities and programs in instruction (Montesur, 2021). Moreover, the P.E program aims to develop the students' physical prowess, agility, endurance, vitality, and kinesthetic skills. Thus, P.E is designed to help students to be mentally sound, physically strong, and emotionally balanced. Next, the Music program, on the other hand, is directed to expose students and pupils to the development of their appreciation for the culture and music of various regions worldwide. In addition, the program allows you to sing music from various genres, play different instruments, and listen to the recordings of various world artists. With this program, they are assisted in creating their own music (Carreon, 2020). Furthermore, the art program, on the other hand, is geared towards the appreciation of students in the fields

of arts and culture in various regions worldwide. It also focuses on the development of art skills, like sketching, painting, coloring, molding, sculpture, and construction of various models/ artworks. In addition, the health program is designed to keep students safe (Miclait, 2019). Therefore, the study has a huge urgency in exploring how teachers addressing issues through creativity and expression can contribute to a more inclusive and socially conscious education. Research in this area can inform teacher training and professional development programs. It can help educators enhance their teaching methods and better meet the needs of their students. Effective assessment of creativity and expression in MAPEH subjects is a challenge. Research can shed light on innovative assessment

methods that align with the goals of these subjects. Findings from such research can influence educational policies and curriculum development. Policymakers may use this information to design curricula prioritizing creativity and expression within MAPEH. In a globalized world, creativity and cultural expression can help individuals and nations stand out. Researching how MAPEH teachers foster these qualities can contribute to national and international competitiveness (Field, 2021). Studying the perceptions and practices of MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and expression is not only timely but also crucial for the continued improvement of education systems worldwide, ensuring that students receive a comprehensive and enriching educational experience (Carreon,2020).

1.1. Purpose of the Study—To examine teachers’ creativity in fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects. To identify the teaching strategies and methods employed by MAPEH teachers to promote creativity and expression in their classrooms and how MAPEH teachers perceive the impact of creativity and self-expression on students’ overall learning experience and personal development. To provide recommendations and best practices for MAPEH teachers and educational policymakers based on the study’s findings.

1.2. Research Questions—Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the different practices based on their lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression?
- (2) How do MAPEH teachers handle creativity and self-expression in students’ overall learning experience and personal development?
- (3) What educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Creativity: The ability to generate original ideas, explore new possibilities, and apply imagination in ways that foster artistic, musical, physical, and expressive abilities, particularly in MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) subjects. It refers to students’ capacity for innovation and self-expression in their learning process.

Self-Expression: The process through which students communicate their thoughts, emotions, and individual identity through vari-

ous forms of art, music, physical activities, and health education in MAPEH classes. It emphasizes the importance of personal voice and uniqueness in learning.

Educational Management: The strategies and practices employed by educators and administrators in organizing, directing, and enhancing the learning environment. In this study, it refers to the insights gained from MAPEH teachers’ practices in managing creativity and self-expression and their impact on students’ learning and personal development.

1.4. Significant of the Study—

The output of this study would benefit the following: Department of Education. The study can help policymakers identify the factors influencing teacher-teaching strategies and develop appropriate interventions to improve these areas. Through this research, policymakers can gain insights into enhancing the quality of teaching strategies that would ensure an effective instructional process. School Administrators. This study can provide valuable insights to school administrators on the current status of teachers' professional development in developing teaching strategies and honing students' learning styles, particularly in MAPEH subjects, in their respective schools. Public and Private Teachers. The study's findings help English teachers identify their students' struggles and develop

appropriate teaching strategies to enhance their students' English identity and academic self-efficacy. Through this research, teachers can also gain insights into effective teaching practices and strategies for promoting greater interest and motivation among their students in English-related subjects. Future Researchers. This study can be a valuable reference and basis for future researchers interested in understanding the factors that shape students' attitudes and beliefs toward English. By building on the insights gained from this study, future researchers can continue to advance the field of MAPEH education and support the learning needs of students as influenced by the teachers' teaching strategies.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The study was anchored first with Jean Piaget's theory of constructivism. Piaget's work on constructivism dates to the early 20th century, with his major works published between the 1920s and 1970s. Constructivism emphasizes that learning is an active process where individuals construct their own knowledge through experiences. In the context of MAPEH, this lens would examine how teachers perceive and facilitate creative and expressive learning experiences. The study was anchored with the theory of Sociocultural Theory: Sociocultural theory by James Wertsch: James Wertsch expanded upon Vygotsky's ideas and published significant works in the latter half of the 20th century and early 21st century. Sociocultural Theory: Sociocultural theory, as advanced by Vygotsky, focuses on the role of social interaction and cultural context in learning. This lens could explore how MAPEH teachers' perceptions and practices are influenced by the sociocultural context in which they teach. The third study was anchored by the theory of Edward Deci and Richard Ryan. Deci and Ryan developed the

Self-Determination Theory in the 1980s, which has continued to evolve with their ongoing research. Self-determination theory emphasizes the importance of intrinsic motivation and autonomy in learning. Researchers using this lens might investigate how teachers' support for students' autonomy and intrinsic motivation affects creativity and expression in MAPEH subjects. Edward Deci and Richard Ryan are the key proponents of Self-Determination. Fourth was anchored with the theory of Elliot Eisner: Elliot Eisner's work on arts-based research and education has been prominent since the latter half of the 20th century and continued into the early 21st century with the theory of Arts-based research incorporates artistic methods (visual arts, music, dance) to explore educational phenomena. Researchers may employ arts-based methods to understand MAPEH teachers' perceptions and practices in fostering creativity and expression. Elliot Eisner is known for his work on arts-based educational research. Lastly, the study anchored Stuart Hall's theory: Stuart Hall's contributions to cultural studies occurred throughout the late 20th century, with

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

influential works published from the 1960s onwards. Henry Giroux: Henry Giroux's work in cultural studies and critical pedagogy has been ongoing since the 1970s. Cultural studies examine how cultural norms, values, and power structures influence education. Researchers adopting this perspective might investigate how culture shapes the perceptions and practices of MAPEH teachers in different contexts. Teachers facilitate opportunities for collaboration and communication among students, fostering a collective creative spirit. Through group projects, discussions, and interactive activities, educators promote the exchange of ideas, ensuring that students learn not only from their teachers but also from each other. Stuart Hall, Henry Giroux, and Paulo Freire have significantly contributed to cultural studies in education. Inclusive Ed-

ucation: An inclusive education perspective ensures all students have equitable access to learning opportunities regardless of their abilities or backgrounds. Researchers may explore how MAPEH teachers' perceptions and practices contribute to inclusive and diverse classrooms. Figure 1 shows the interconnection between the two research questions, the best practices based on their lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression, and the mechanism by which the MAPEH teachers manage creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development that would result in the common denominator, which is Insights Learned from the experiences of lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression,

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the researcher introduced the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research participants, design and procedure, data collection, data analysis, ethical considerations, the role of the researcher, and trustworthiness.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—It was assumed that all participants answered interview questions honestly and to the best of their abilities. The sample used for this study was further assumed to be representative of in-depth interviews as a medium of communication. These beliefs have been called paradigms (Lincoln, 2019), philosophical assumptions, epistemologies, and ontologies (Crotty, 2020), broadly conceived research methodologies (Neuman, 2020), and alternative knowledge claims (Creswell, 2019). There are beliefs about ontology, the nature of reality, epistemology, what counts as knowledge and how knowledge claims are justified, axiology, the role of values in research, and methodology (the process of research. In this discussion. Ontology. The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics, when researchers conduct qualitative research, they are embracing the idea of analyzing teachers' perceptions of MAPEH teachers' practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects. Different researchers embrace different realities, as do the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 2019). Epistemology. Conducting a qualitative study means that the researcher tries to get as close as possible to the participants being studied. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. The very reason why I chose these high school teachers as my participants is that I have known them for quite a long time. This is how knowledge is known through the subjective experiences of people. It becomes important, then, to conduct studies in the “field” where the participants live and work; these are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the “field” or get to know the participants, the more they “know what they know” from firsthand information. For example, good phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site (Wolcott, 2019). Axiology. This assumption characterizes qualitative research. How does the researcher implement this assumption in practice? In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. This means that the result of this study was shared with the school where I am currently working. We say that they “position themselves” in a study. In an interpretive biography, for example, the researcher’s presence is apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 2019).

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—

The researcher made these qualitative assumptions that consist of the methods used in the process of qualitative research (Creswell, 2019). The procedures used by the researcher are inductive and based on the researcher's experience in collecting and analyzing data. The research here is the product of the values of the researcher. Through an inductive approach, raw textual data is condensed into a brief, summary format. Clear links are established between research objectives and summary findings derived from raw data. A framework of the underlying structure of experiences or processes that are evident from the raw data is developed. A phenomenological study describes the meaning of the lived experiences of individuals about a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2019) was used in this study. A key characteristic of this approach is to study how members of a group or community interpret themselves, the world, and life around them (Mertens, 2019). The Purposive sampling was utilized in this study to analyze teachers' teachers' perceptions of MAPEH teachers' practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects in high

school classrooms was using effective instructional practices, related to building background, student interactions, and application, to meet the needs of learners as well as the possible challenges experienced by teachers when implementing these practices as pedagogy in the teaching-learning process. Collectively, these results may provide foundational information to guide the district in addressing the local issue. Administrators might benefit from this information as it might enable them to make informed decisions about what support is needed for analyzing teachers' teachers' perceptions of MAPEH teachers' practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects. In addition, this study was to discover analyzing teachers' teachers' perceptions of MAPEH teachers' practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects in selected junior high school teachers, appear to have experienced analyzing teachers' perceptions in practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects, specifically in the areas of building background knowledge, interactions, and application.

2.3. Design and Procedure—In the next section, the specific details of the research procedures were described, so future researchers can generalize the results from this study to other situations. Extensive and careful descriptions of the time, place, context, and culture of the study was thoroughly discussed to develop transferability, which is the qualitative parallel to external validity in post-positivist research (Mertens, 2020). This section was: discuss the interview approach; explain the role of the researcher; and lastly, (describe the sampling method and ethical considerations. Qualitative interviewing is not used to get answers to questions but to understand the experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of that experience (Seidman, 2019). Generally,

qualitative studies use unstructured, open-ended interviews because they allow for the most flexibility and responsiveness to emerging issues for both the participants and interviewer; however, the use of semi-structured interviews is not uncommon and used when the researcher seeks to obtain specific, more focused information (Schwandt, 2021). Semi-structured interviews combine the flexibility of unstructured, open-ended interviews with directionality and an agenda to produce focused, qualitative, textual data (Schensul LeCompte, 2019). This study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore how junior high school teachers describe how teachers analyze their perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. An interview

guide was used to ensure that the same information was collected from all the participants. The interview guide included open-ended questions and topics to help structure the interview. However, when needed, the interviewer also explored, probed, and asked additional questions to clarify and expand on a particular topic. The interview guide helped make interviewing several participants more systematic and comprehensive by defining the issues to be explored (Patton, 2019). The open-ended questions were framed in a way that allowed the participants to

represent their views and perspectives in their own words and terms, in addition to taking the questions in any direction that they chose (Patton, 2020). Since qualitative research studies subjects in their natural setting, all interviews except one took place using a face-to-face format at a time convenient for the participants. All interview sessions were tape-recorded for transcription. When needed, the researcher used follow-up interviews after transcription to clarify meaning or explore areas in more depth.

2.4. Research Participants—The study comprised a unique group of ten (10) participants, all of whom were active public high school faculty members during the 2023-2024 academic year. These individuals, who were still teaching and handling the MAPEH subject, were selected from a pool of faculty from various public schools. The selection process was purposeful, resulting in a sample of twelve (12) junior high school teachers. The researcher used purposive sampling also known as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling, wherein

is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. This survey sampling method requires research to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies so that they can properly choose and approach eligible participants to be conducted (Denzin, 2019). The participants of this study are the junior high school teachers from the selected public schools in the Division of Island Garden City of Samal. Below is a simple description of the participants.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical standards are required in conducting research; thus, this phenomenological research adheres to the principles of the Belmont Report (2019), which strictly observes the principles of respect of persons, beneficence, and justice. Specifically, this study was subjected to the evaluation of the Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. – Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) for the entire board review of the ethical aspects of the investigation as regards the dimensions of research ethics that include social value, informed consent, vulnerability issues, risk-benefit ratio, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities and community involve-

ment. Social Value. The researcher investigated and carefully analyzed one of the pressing problems in our educational system. Also, this research analyzes teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. This study is expected to provide important information in recognizing the extent and type of experiences that basic education teachers experience. The findings of this study can provide more insights among basic education teachers and students to maintain quality teaching and learning. The researcher is hopeful that the study's output is relevant not only to the participants but also to the school. The study's results would be presented in local, national, and even international fora and,

if given a chance, published in an international publication. Informed consent. In this study, informed consent was secured from all the participants who were involved. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to twelve (12) junior high school teachers. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The participants had sufficient information and an adequate understanding of both the proposal and the implications of their participation in the study. Codes were assigned to individuals in the data presented. Every page of the transcriptions of the in-depth interview and focus group discussions was signed by the researcher to attest that the key informant interviews were done with the consent of informants. In addition, the informants were accorded the needed respect. The researcher made it a point that the form must bear the signature of the participant or agreement, which would imply that she participated in the study voluntarily. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The researcher protected the participants from being deceived, threatened, and forced to participate. The researcher treated them with the highest respect. Thus, they were informed ahead of time that they might withdraw their participation in the study, and if any inconvenience was felt during the interview and in answering the questionnaire, they would be given a chance to raise their concern and opt to cancel the activity. Although the participants were all of legal age, 18 years old and above, they were still vulnerable because the researcher is a junior high school teacher in Kaputian District, Division of Island Garden City Samal, as one of the selected research locales of the study. Teachers were treated with utmost respect so they would not be vulnerable while participating in this study. The researcher considered the basic junior high school teachers participants in this study because they were mature enough to decide whether to participate. Risks-Benefit

Safety. A careful assessment of foreseeable risks, burdens, and benefits to the participants was made. The questionnaire the researcher administered did not contain any degrading, discriminating, or unacceptable language that was offensive to the participants, so the risks were avoided. An extra careful approach was used in collecting the data so that irrelevant and confidential details were rejected. The study did not involve any high-risk situation the participants may experience in their social and emotional needs. Further, this study ensured that the potential benefits of the participants were more significant than the potential harm. The results of this study would benefit the entire department of education; teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to synthesize various activities that would address the analyzing teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. Practically the researcher identified only minimal risks if not negligible regarding physical harm or discomfort that they may experience during the conduct of the study. Specifically, whatever might cause adverse effects on personal relationships, loss of status, privacy, or time of the respondents were taken into consideration in the planning stage of the conduct of the study so that such things would be minimized if not prevented fully. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The current study ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents' information. The researcher adhered to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, or Republic Act 10173, which mandates transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in the collection, retention, and processing of personal information (Congress of the Philippines, 2022). This act protected the fundamentals of human rights on the privacy of information, ensuring the free flow of information that promotes innovation and growth. The researcher protected the respondent/participants' right to privacy, wherein

their responses were given with the highest respect. Unless the law requires, the confidentiality of information shall always be observed. Other personal information was not requested in the study to safeguard their identities and enable them to participate without any fear of being revealed to be involved in the study. Any information was taken with utmost care to ensure the data sources' anonymity and de-identify any personal information that would be shared. Such names and identities were protected by using a pseudonym. The information on these codes was transcribed in an archival log. Hence, personal names were not used to trace the identification. Written responses, if any, were captured through a camera. Recordings were saved, and documents were kept in one place, protected or encrypted. Justice. In this study, justice requires an equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research. There was a fair selection in population, sampling, and assignments. Provision of appropriate care to research participants regardless of their economic status, gender, race, or creed was provided. With this, the researcher assured the respondents who were involved were appropriate for the study. The researcher provided just compensation and reimbursement for the data used and costs incurred by the participants. The participants were adequately informed of the study's objectives before they were involved in the process. They were emphasized as the data source and encouraged to give honest answers in the survey questionnaire. In return, they were the priority for the benefits of the possible offshoots of the study findings. Transparency. To be ethical, all the parties need to be transparent by ensuring that the process, the nature of the study, and the extent of participation are clear and understandable to the participants. The researcher was transparent about the aspects of the study, especially the information that has a bearing on the decision of participants to give or withhold their informed consent. The par-

ticipants can access and scrutinize the study's findings to determine if the findings are scientifically valid and have significant implications for the participant's well-being. The researcher assured us that the study was conveyed in full scope and with accuracy. Specifically, in qualitative data analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected accordingly. Moreover, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision. Consequently, the researcher ensured the reasonable availability and accessibility of the research outcomes to the Department of Education, teachers, students, parents, and the community. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher is ultimately responsible and accountable for the research. The research needs to be carried out with the necessary skills and knowledge. I am aware of the limits of personal competence in research. With my experience as a junior high school master teacher 1, in public schools Kaputian District, Division of Island Garden City of Samal. I attended several research-related seminars and training which I consider an asset in conducting this study with the assistance of my adviser and colleagues, readings from various books and literature, fulfilling my duties and responsibilities at the Kaputian District as a junior high school master teacher 1, I acquired the knowledge and skills needed to conduct the research. Also, the supervision and direction of his adviser and the panelists helped improve the research study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher adequately has the budget and equipment to conduct the study. This was to ensure that the researcher had the best facilities to complete the research. The researcher personally owned the laptop, printer, internet connection, and other facilities, making the facilities adequately and readily available. Furthermore, library resources, both non-online and online, are readily available, such as books and Google. In addition, if possible, Google Meet was used in gathering the data. Aside from the enumerated resources, some ex-

perts, like the adviser, RMC-Research Ethics Committee, and panel members, who are also the expert validators, provided the researcher with the guidance needed in the conduct of this research. Community Involvement. The researcher is engaged with communities like the Public Schools academic community, teachers, parents, and basic education students since I am a teacher in one of the public schools in the Kaputian District, Division of Island Garden City of Samal is composed of quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects the cultural, traditional, and religious practices of the community. The RMC graduate school helped in correcting, validating, and revising the manuscript of the current study. The RMC graduate school provided directions to the researcher based on its research standards and

practices. The involvement of the junior high school teachers, students, and parents, participated in the development of the questionnaire through the output of the first phase of the study. The guide questions were the instrument for gathering qualitative data in the second phase. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools as my target participants were observed. Moreover, the significant personas in the public school organizational landscape and other stakeholders may benefit from the study's output because they were the recipients of the data regarding knowledge about MAPEH teachers' perceptions of their practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—Following signing consent forms, they analyzed teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms using semi-structured, in-depth interviews. Data was organized and analyzed. The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in a circle to ensure we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis (Mazuwelics, 2018). Thematic Content Analysis. This was used to interpret the responses made by the key participants in determining the lessons and insights derived from the views of analyzing perceptions in MAPEH teachers' practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects. Their responses were processed and conducted through analyses. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of

the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interviews may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. In this phase, the researcher may use thematic analysis in analyzing the gathered data. Their responses were processed and conducted through analysis. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interview may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. Environmental Triangulation. Triangulation analysis is a tool developed by Margaret Schuler to help advocates perform a strategic analysis of the issues they are working on. The tool looks at three different aspects: content, structure, and culture. Triangular analysis

is a technique for both analyzing and finding answers to a problem, structured around structure, content, and culture in the policy system. It was done through transcribing, member checking, and triangulation. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with

2.7. *Data Collection*—Before the data gathering, I was asking for the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges to pursue the study. After the permissions were approved by the school division Superintendent and the school principals of the target participants, the researcher talked to the participants to acquaint them with the purpose of the study. I agree with the participants on the most convenient date and time for the conduct of the interview. To start the interview, I asked the participants to read the respondents' consent and to affix their signatures on the consent paper after they were oriented on the purpose of the study and agreed on the terms and conditions. The researcher would emphasize to the respondents that they are allowed to ask questions to clarify any matter regarding the study and ask their consent to record the course of the conversation with the assurance that everything shall be dealt with the utmost confidentiality. Through in-depth interviews, I was able to gather the feelings, reactions, observations, and experiences of the teachers in their conduct towards sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils. The interview included the gathering of information as to obstacles and challenges that the teachers encounter with the home visits. I likewise aimed to obtain substantial information exploring Miles and Huberman (2020), considering the teacher's perspectives on the personality development of pupils and the interventions that help bridge the risk of understanding and make science subjects more realistic experiences for the pupils. In an-

the participants in taking circle to ensure that we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis. To achieve a truthful and productive result in a qualitative study, the researcher must possess trustworthiness and credibility requirements (Mazuwelics, 2019).

analyzing the data gathered, the participants' narratives were transcribed. According to Koontz and Weinrich (2020), the process and narratives do not need to be transcribed verbatim if the essence of what the participants were communicating has been caught in the transcription. Individual transcriptions of the interview were validated by the respective participants. To verify and revalidate the data gathered, I conducted focus group discussions to validate and triangulate the information gathered. Corrections may be made according to the participants' feedback to ensure that the meaning was conveyed in the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. Data was collected from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Field notes were used to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and were based on an interview guide. Data was generated through field notes, a voice recorder, or cellphone videos during participant interviews. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedules. The interval between interviews was, on average, one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions were also made to clarify

ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over high quality attributes. In a qualitative phenomenological study, research data involved the researcher spending as much time as possible with the teachers at the high schools to gain an in-depth understanding of the junior high school teachers in their everyday lives. Participant observations of the secondary faculty behaviors, beliefs, traditions, culture, and social and emotional interactions were recorded in a journal at the end of each day. Where applicable, in-depth interviews were conducted in field settings and were either recorded, transcribed, and/or summarized in the journal. As an active participant in the research process, the researcher constantly evaluated her role and hand relationship with participants and applied this to develop an understanding and interpretation of the basic education teacher's social and emotional worlds (Unger, 2020). This resulted in an evolving research process in terms of the direction and type of data derived and in terms of a personal transformation for the researcher. The evolution of the research as a relational transformation between a researcher open to a new experience and a community of participants cannot be overemphasized. The results of this study could not have been foreseen at the inception of this study (Parker, 2020). As noted earlier, the study's location is an academic institution that experienced changes in its teaching methods. The researcher already spent several years as a junior high school teacher, so I had a great chance to gather demographic information and meet as many of the locals as possible. Also, it was hoped that partici-

pant observation could provide an initial understanding of the community's culture. All participants signed an informed consent form before being interviewed. The researcher translated the questionnaires into the language commonly used by the participants. Data collection was multimodal. According to Yin (2020), the main characteristic of phenomenological qualitative research is that it employs various data collection methods to ensure the report's trustworthiness. Multiple data sources promote a clearer understanding of the data being studied. Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were collected. Field notes were used to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and were based on an interview guide (Creswell et al., 2019). Data was generated through field notes, a voice recorder, or cellphone videos during participant interviews. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedules. The interval between interviews was, on average, one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions would also clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over high-quality attributes.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—Qualitative data analysis begins with the process of organizing, reducing, and describing the collected data (Schwandt, 2021). Unlike quantitative analysis, there are no prescribed formulas for qualitative

analysis. Marshall and Rossman (2020) remind researchers that qualitative analysis does not proceed linearly and is not neat. However, good practice and procedures enhance the credibility of qualitative research. In this last section,

the data analysis procedures were explained, and the steps taken to ensure the results from this study are credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic will be thoroughly described. To guide the data analysis, the researcher used the seven phases of data analysis described by Marshall and Rossman (2020) to reduce data, create manageable pieces, allow for interpretation, and find meaning in the words of the participants. The seven phases included organizing the data, immersion in the data, generating categories and themes, coding the data, offering interpretations through analytic memos, and searching for alternative understandings (Marshall Rossman, 2020). Data analysis first begins with organizing the data. The organization of the data involved keeping information provided by each participant separate and in sequence with the order of the interviews. Organizing the data allowed it to remain manageable, easily accessible, and readily available. The digital audio files from the interviews were carefully transcribed into written form. Electronic folders were established to organize the data collected from each participant. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data by reading the interviews extensively to understand their content. This involved reading through the interviews at least three times. Following Hatch's (2022) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2022). After the initial readings, Hatch (2022) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology

2.9. Framework of Analysis—It was shown in the analytical framework in the analysis of perceptions of MAPEH teachers' practices of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects and inclination for growth development, which is most effective

in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems made up of categories that divide some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2022), theories, common sense, or research objectives generate typologies. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature review as the constructs through which to view the data. After reading through the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began the process of offering interpretations. During this stage, the researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences by pulling salient themes, reoccurring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2020) believe this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in analyzing. Rossman and Marshall (2020) remind researchers that the data would always have alternate explanations. Before proceeding, the researcher stops and evaluates the findings for other plausible explanations.

in teaching-learning. Also, teachers' demands and parents' supervision affected learners' interest in what their experience was to be divulged and brought new insight and hope to upcoming similar situations or cases. The experiences were analyzed to provide insight and feelings on

making a difference in the educational system. Both aim to provide information on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pups, analyzing teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed to search for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. The analytical framework for this study was flexible enough to allow the researcher to either gather all of the data and then analyze it or evaluate it while it was being collected. The data collected was then sifted, charted, and categorized in line with key topics and themes during the analysis stage. This process involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization was becoming familiar with the data through reading and re-reading interview transcripts. Familiarizing the whole interview with the audio recording and transcript and any contextual or reflective notes the researcher recorded was a vital stage in interpretation. It could also be helpful to re-listen to all or parts of the audio recording. The researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, exploring the field, or reading transcripts. The researcher would become aware of critical ideas and recurring themes throughout the procedure and would make a note of them. The researcher may be unable to review all of the material due to the enormous amount of data that might be collected in qualitative research. As a result, a portion of the data set would be utilized. Several elements of the data collection method would influence the selection. Coding was the process of summarizing and representing data in order to provide a systematic account of the recorded or observed phenomenon. After familiarization, the researcher carefully reads the transcript line

by line, applying a paraphrase or label that is a 'code' that describes what they have interpreted in the passage as necessary. Coding aimed to classify all of the data to be compared systematically with other parts of the data set. Developing a thematic framework happens after coding a few transcripts. The researcher needs to compare the labels applied and select a set of codes to apply to all subsequent transcripts. Codes could be grouped into categories, which are then clearly defined. This forms a working analytical framework. Several iterations of the analytical framework were likely required before no additional codes emerged. It was always worth having another code under each category to avoid ignoring data that does not fit; the analytical framework was never 'final' until the last transcript had been coded. Indexing involves identifying portions or sections of data that relate to a specific theme. This procedure is conducted using all textual data collected, such as transcripts of interviews. Ritchie and Spencer (1994) suggest using a numerical system to index references and annotating them in the margin beside the text for ease. Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for this task. Charting involves summarizing the data by category from each transcript. Good charting requires an ability to strike a balance between reducing the data on the one hand and retaining the original meanings and 'feel' of the interviewees' words on the other. The chart should include references to interesting or illustrative quotations. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, includes an analysis of the important qualities depicted in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, assisting the researcher in interpreting the data set. I must be cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis and define concepts, map the range and nature of phenomena, create typologies, find associations, provide explanations, and develop strategies (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). These concepts, technologies, and asso-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

ciations mirror the participant. Therefore, any strategies or recommendations the researcher offers reflect the participants’ real views, beliefs, and values. Figure 2 shows the steps in

the process of the study’s analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Qualitative research does not claim to be replicable. The researcher purposefully avoids controlling the research conditions and concentrates on recording the complexity of situational contexts and interrelations as they occur naturally (Marshall Rossman, 2020). This study took many extra steps to ensure the results from the data

analysis were credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic. Credibility. Mertens (2020) defines credibility as a correspondence between the way a participant perceives social constructs and the way the researcher portrays the participant’s viewpoints. To ensure credibility in this study, the researcher used persistent observation that allowed for interviews that were

long enough to identify salient issues (Mertens, 2020). Transferability. Establishing transferability provides the degree to which the results can be generalized to other situations. The researcher kept an audit trail, which is a meticulous record of the research process so other researchers can recapture steps and the same conclusions (Mertens, 2020). Not only was the data kept, but also the evidence of how the data were reduced, analyzed, and synthesized as well as the process notes that reflect the ongoing inner thoughts, hunches, and reactions of the researcher (Newton Rudestam, 2021). Conformability. “Conformability means that the data and the interpretation are not figments of the researcher’s imagination” (Mertens, 2019). In this study, the data gathered was analyzed and interpreted properly to arrive at a convincing theme that would further discuss the importance of analyzing. To establish conformability, the researcher kept track of the qualitative data

so it could be tracked to its source in the interviews. Authenticity. The researcher presents a balanced view of all perspectives, values, and beliefs to establish authenticity within the study. As a researcher, I must avoid bias in gathering the data. The researcher also monitored her developing constructions and documented any changes she experienced from the beginning of the study to the end in the analytic memos. This procedure began with the researcher’s disclosure of values, beliefs, and experiences that connect her to the topic of analyzing teachers’ perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. This study analyzing teachers’ perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms used peer debriefing to play the role is asking tough questions about the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretations (Newton Rudestam, 2021).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, which focused on the fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects: teachers practice in focus to answer the research questions What are the different practices based on their lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression? How do MAPEH teachers manage to handle creativity and self-expression in students’ overall learning experience and personal development? What educational management or insights are drawn from the study findings? Additionally, the study may aim to identify specific mindfulness-based subjects, to examine the fostering of creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects: teachers practice in focus, to identify the teaching strategies and methods employed by MAPEH teachers to promote creativity and expression in their classrooms, and how do MAPEH teachers perceive the impact of creativity and self-expression on students’ overall learning experience and personal development, to explore the relationship between teacher qualifications, experience, and their perceptions and practices in promoting creativity and expression in MAPEH, to investigate the impact of fostering creativity and expression in MAPEH on students’ academic performance, engagement, and overall development, to provide recommendations and best practices for MAPEH teachers and educational policymakers based on the findings of the study. The researcher begins the discussion by establishing a strong foundation of observation before presenting quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, the Researcher used codes to refer to participants of the research question. Their responses were contained and bounded around the study’s three (3) research questions.

Moreover, participants' responses were transcribed verbatim, translated into English, encoded, and summarized in matrix form, which led to a schema.

3.1. Adapting Pedagogical Approaches to Cultivate Individuality, Holistic Approaches, and Diverse Strategies.—The first objective of this study is to know about the different practices based on their lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having three major themes from the opinion and ideas and narration from the key informant.

3.1.1. Adapting Pedagogical Approaches to Cultivate Individuality—Adaptive teaching is an approach that tailors instruction to meet the unique needs of each learner. This method offers a supportive and engaging learning environment that empowers students to take control of their own learning, discover their passions, and achieve their full potential. It highlights that the lived experience among MAPEH teachers underscores the significance of personalized pedagogical approaches in nurturing creativity and self-expression (Lidser, K. 2022). Recent proponents advocate for a student-centered approach that acknowledges and celebrates individual differences. This fosters a classroom environment where students feel empowered to express themselves authentically through various mediums. Based on the narration from teachers' lived experiences, exploring the lived experiences of MAPEH teachers reveals diverse practices to foster creativity and self-expression among students. These practices include personalized pedagogical approaches tailored to individual student needs, integrating technology and interdisciplinary activities to engage students effectively, creating a supportive classroom environment through positive teacher-student relationships, promoting collaborative projects, and co-creation. The transcripts of participants of the focus interview Answer the research question and connected to Adapting Pedagogical Approaches to Cultivate Individuality, which highlighted that MAPEH teachers have shared a range of practices based on their lived experiences, including integrating various disciplines like music and visual arts, physical activities, and health discussions to provide a comprehensive platform for creative expression. They emphasize the importance of open-ended assignments, encouraging students to explore their interests and express themselves freely. Supported by the idea of Garcia (2020) in the learning process, strategies to support emotional well-being, implementation of experiential learning opportunities to provide hands-on artistic experiences, cultivation of a growth mindset to encourage resilience and experimentation, emphasis on cultural diversity through inclusive curriculum design, and provision of constructive feedback to facilitate students' artistic growth and development.

3.1.2. Holistic Approaches—Teachers also promote experimentation and improvisation, fostering a culture of creative risk-taking. Collaborative projects and peer feedback cultivate community and support within the classroom. Additionally, reflective practices, differentiated instruction, and real-world applications empower students to develop their creative skills and express themselves authentically. A prominent theme emerging from the teachers' responses to the research question "What are the different practices based on their lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression? is

Holistic Approaches to cultivating creative expression. Based on the interview data gathered from teachers' lived experiences in exploring holistic approaches, participants expressed that self-reflection and self-assessment strategies help students deepen their understanding of their creative processes and take ownership of their growth (Malvin et al., 2022). This theme encompasses practices employed by MAPEH teachers, including integrating multiple disciplines such as music, visual arts, physical activities, and health discussions, providing open-ended assignments, encouraging experimentation and improvisation, fostering collaboration and community, and promoting self-reflection and self-assessment. These practices collectively reflect a holistic approach to nurturing students' creative abilities across different dimensions, fostering a sense of ownership and exploration. Based on the analysis of narration from the interview data gathered towards the lived experiences of teachers, the researcher analyzed the narration from the lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression, which is a holistic

3.1.3. Diverse Strategies for Empowering Student Expression—On the other hand, the third theme encompasses various practices employed by MAPEH teachers. A theme that emerges from the teachers' responses to the research question about fostering creativity and self-expression is "Diverse Strategies for Empowering Student Expression." This theme reflects the wide range of approaches MAPEH teachers employ to nurture creativity and self-expression among students. It encompasses practices such as integrating multiple disciplines, offering open-ended assignments, encouraging experimentation, fostering collaboration, promoting reflection, implementing differentiated instruction, leveraging technology, incorporating real-world applications, and creating supportive classroom environments. To-

gether, these diverse strategies aim to empower students to express themselves authentically and cultivate their creative abilities across various dimensions. Based on the analysis of the narration from the lived experiences through the interview and data gathered shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression, answered the research question and connected to the third theme, which is a compelling theme from the lived experiences shared by MAPEH (Music et al. Education, and Health) teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression is diverse strategies aim to empower students to express themselves authentically and cultivate their creative abilities across various dimensions. In the narrative of teachers fostering creativity and self-expression, a diverse array of strategies is employed to empower stu-

dents to authentically express themselves and develop their creative abilities across various dimensions. These strategies encompass a multifaceted approach that acknowledges each student's unique needs, interests, and talents while fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment. On the other hand, the narration of teachers' participants claims that there were struggles of MAPEH teachers teaching MAPEH subjects, especially those teachers who were not MAPEH majors, and they continued to justify that MAPEH subject is not MAPEH lang subject. MAPEH subjects demand more effort, expertise, dedication, strategies, approaches, and knowledge on how to teach them effectively. The study by Nordly (2019) supports the need for improving the professional preparation of physical education and sports teachers' aperiodic and through a program of evaluation. He added that one of the real values of in-service growth is meeting the inadequacy of pre-service education for teachers. Likewise, he emphasized that every mentor must be adept in exercising his profession to promote the continuous improvement of his duties toward the school system's curriculum. In-service training. One of the critical strategies highlighted by teachers is the integration of multiple disciplines within the MAPEH curriculum. By incorporating music, visual arts, physical activities, and health discussions, teachers provide students with a rich and diverse platform for creative exploration. This interdisciplinary approach stimulates students' imaginations and encourages them to make meaningful connections between different forms of expression. Open-ended assignments are another crucial strategy teachers employ to promote creativity and self-expression. These assignments allow students the freedom to explore their interests, experiment with different mediums, and take ownership of their creative process. By encouraging students to think outside the box and pursue their passions, teachers empower them to develop their unique artistic voices. Additionally, teachers employ reflective practices to help students deepen their understanding of their creative processes and progress. By encouraging students to reflect on their work, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and set goals for future growth, teachers empower them to take ownership of their artistic development. Differentiated instruction ensures that all students can participate meaningfully in creative expression, regardless of their learning styles or abilities. Teachers tailor their instruction to meet the diverse needs of their students, providing individualized support and encouragement as needed. Dulay (2022) stated the coping mechanisms of the Teachers in MAPEH in terms of Time Management, Academic Advice, and Mentoring Appraisal Focused and Emotional-Focused. Do the coping mechanisms teachers use significantly affect the performance of non-specialized teachers teaching MAPEH? Therefore, the study urgently explores how teachers addressing issues through creativity and expression can contribute to a more inclusive and socially conscious education. Research in this area can inform teacher training and professional development programs. It can help educators enhance their teaching methods and better meet the needs of their students. Practical assessment of creativity and expression in MAPEH subjects is a challenge. Research can shed light on innovative assessment methods that align with the goals of these subjects. Figure 3 shows the teachers' lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression and the emergence of the three themes: adapting pedagogical approaches, holistic approaches, and diverse Strategies

3.2. The MAPEH Teachers Handle Creativity and Self-Expression In Students' Overall Learning Experience and Personal Development—

Fig. 3. The teachers' lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression

The art program, on the other hand, is geared towards the appreciation of the students in the arts and culture of various regions worldwide. It also focuses on developing art skills, like sketching, painting, coloring, molding, sculpture, and construction of various models/ artworks. In addition, the health program is designed to keep students (Miclath, 2019). The second objective of this study is to identify the teaching strategies and methods employed by MAPEH teachers to promote creativity and expression in their classrooms and how they perceive the impact of creativity and

self-expression on students' overall learning experience and personal development. Therefore, based on the research questions, the study dealt with the teachers' coping mechanism with the challenges of MAPEH teachers on how to manage to handle creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development, considering the first theme empowering through creative engagement, underscores the central role of creativity and self-expression in MAPEH education, highlighting their transformative impact on student's academic success and holistic development.

3.2.1. Empowering Through Creative Engagement—Based on the research questions present a compelling exploration of how MAPEH teachers navigate the challenges of fostering creativity and self-expression in students. The emphasis on the first theme, "Empowering Through Creative Engagement," effectively underscores the critical role of creativity and self-expression in MAPEH education. The narrative aptly highlights the transformative impact of creativity and self-expression on students' academic success and holistic development. By providing a comprehensive platform for creative exploration and expression, MAPEH teachers empower students to engage with diverse artistic expression forms and develop essential lifelong learning skills. From integrating multiple disciplines to creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment, teachers are depicted as proactive facilitators who encourage students to take ownership of their learning and express themselves authentically. Overall, the narrative offers valuable insights into the challenges faced by MAPEH teachers and the strategies they employ to promote creativity and self-expression. Likewise, based on the narration of based on the research questions offers a profound exploration of the challenges faced by MAPEH teachers in fos-

tering creativity and self-expression in students and communicates the fundamental importance of creativity and self-expression in MAPEH education. The narrative eloquently underscores the transformative impact of creativity and self-expression on students' academic success and holistic development. This is supported by the idea of Field, (2021). Studying the perceptions and practices of MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and expression is not only timely but also crucial for the continued improvement of education systems worldwide, ensuring that students receive a comprehensive and enriching educational experience. Supported with the idea of Carreon, (2020), creativity and cultural expression can help individuals and nations stand out. Researching how MAPEH teachers foster these qualities can contribute to national and international competitiveness. By highlighting the central role of creativity and self-expression in MAPEH education, the narrative effectively communicates the importance of nurturing these qualities in students for their overall academic success and personal development. Indeed, MAPEH, as a key learning area, is of major significance in the development of all the learners in various grade levels in the Philippine Secondary Schools. MAPEH in its four components is designed to develop students holisti-

cally. In addition, the word holistically is too heavy to carry if the ones responsible for teaching the latter are out-of-field and do not have

enough knowledge and training to execute all its components (Silvestre, 2020).

3.2.2. Navigating Constraints to Foster Creative Empowerment—On the other hand, based on the research questions, the study dealt with the teacher’s coping with the challenges of MAPEH. Teachers manage to handle creativity and self-expression in students’ overall learning experience and personal development considering the second theme, *Navigating Constraints to Foster Creative Empowerment*. This theme encapsulates the challenges MAPEH teachers face in managing creativity and self-expression in students’ overall learning experience and personal development within the context of empowering through creative engagement. It highlights the complexities teachers encounter, including standardized curricula, limited resources, and diverse student needs, as they strive to create environments conducive to nurturing students’ creative potential. Based on the narrative adeptly portrays MAPEH teachers as proactive facilitators who employ diverse strategies to cultivate creativity and self-expression in their classrooms. From integrating various disciplines to creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment, teachers are depicted as dedicated professionals who empower students to express themselves authentically. Likewise, the teachers’ narration provides a nuanced exploration of the challenges faced by MAPEH teachers in nurturing creativity and self-expression among students, highlighting the critical role of these qualities in shaping students’ overall learning experience and personal development. By centering on the theme of “*Navigating Constraints to Foster Creative Empowerment*,” the narrative effectively emphasizes the importance of creativity and self-expression within the MAPEH curriculum. Moreover, teachers’ participants’ narration, the narrative skillfully portrays MAPEH

teachers as proactive agents of change who actively seek out innovative strategies to cultivate creativity and self-expression in their classrooms. From integrating cross-disciplinary connections to fostering collaborative learning environments, teachers are depicted as dedicated professionals committed to empowering students to unleash their creative potential and develop a strong sense of self-expression. Supported by the ideas of Malvin Quiles Dulay (2022), learners with unique talents in sports, dances, and physical activities should be recognized and given more extensive training to improve their amateur sports. However, it is sad to note that not all teachers have sufficient knowledge and skills to deliver instructions effectively. Some may be musically inclined, have skills and knowledge in the arts, have experience and knowledge in different sports, and may be knowledgeable in health. However, only a few have the required skills in all these components, considering that the MAPEH curriculum is equally important with all the other learning areas. Overall, the narrative compellingly portrays the challenges and opportunities inherent in fostering creativity and self-expression in MAPEH education. One notable aspect of the narrative is its recognition of the multifaceted nature of creativity and self-expression, acknowledging that these qualities extend beyond traditional artistic endeavors to encompass a wide range of disciplines and activities. This inclusive approach reflects a deep understanding of the diverse ways students can engage with and express themselves creatively, enriching their academic experiences and fostering their holistic development. By emphasizing the transformative impact of these qualities on students’ academic success and holistic develop-

ment, the narrative effectively underscores their significance in shaping the future of education. Additionally, the narrative effectively communicates the transformative impact of creativity and self-expression on students' academic success and personal growth. By highlighting their role

in enhancing critical thinking skills, fostering collaboration, and promoting emotional well-being, the narrative underscores the profound influence of these qualities on students' overall development and future success (Crisanto Daga, 2021).

3.2.3. Cultivate Creative Empowerment— On the other hand, based on the research questions, the study dealt with the teachers cope with the challenges of MAPEH teachers managing to handle creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development, considering the third theme based on research question 2, which is Cultivate Creative Empowerment. MAPEH fosters creativity and self-expression within the framework of empowering through creative engagement. It highlights the various constraints, such as standardized curricula, limited resources, and diverse student needs, that teachers must navigate to nurture students' creative potential effectively. Despite these challenges, MAPEH teachers remain committed to creating inclusive and supportive environments where students feel empowered to express themselves authentically, thus fostering their overall learning experience and personal development. Based on the analyzed narration of teachers coping with the challenges of narrative, it offers a compelling and insightful exploration of how MAPEH teachers navigate the challenges of fostering creativity and self-expression in their classrooms. By strongly emphasizing the theme of "Cultivate Creative Empowerment," the narrative effectively underscores the central importance of these qualities in MAPEH education and their transformative impact on students' lives. Likewise, the narration from teachers coping stated that it deals with the intricate landscape of MAPEH education, shedding light on the challenges teachers face in nurturing creativity and self-expression among students. By centering on the theme

of "MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression within the framework of empowering through creative engagement. It highlights the various constraints, such as standardized curricula, limited resources, and diverse student needs, that teachers must navigate to effectively nurture students' creative potential. Despite these challenges, MAPEH teachers remain committed to creating inclusive and supportive environments where students feel empowered to express themselves authentically, thus fostering their overall learning experience and personal development," the narrative effectively portrays creativity and self-expression as essential components of the MAPEH curriculum, crucial for students' academic success and holistic development. However, only a few have the required skills in all these components, considering that MAPEH curriculum is equally important with all the other learning areas. Given the foregoing facts and the consideration that MAPEH contributes significantly to the holistic development of the learners, the researcher was motivated to determine the present status of MAPEH in terms of its implementation. Hence, this study was thought of. Hopefully, through this study, the weaknesses and problems of the MAPEH program that might be disclosed will attract the concerned authorities to their resolution towards enhancing students' learning outcomes (Montesur, 2021). This holistic approach reflects an understanding of the interconnectedness of creativity and self-expression with students' overall learning experience and personal growth. Furthermore, the narrative vividly depicts MAPEH teachers as innovative educators

Fig. 4. MAPEH teachers manage to handle creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development

who constantly adapt and evolve their teaching practices to meet their students' diverse needs. By integrating various teaching strategies and methods, such as cross-disciplinary connections and collaborative learning environments, teachers empower students to explore and express themselves creatively in ways that resonate with their interests and strengths (Stead, R 2019). Supported by Tabuena (2021), by understanding the perspectives of MAPEH teachers, educational policies can be improved to enhance the quality of instruction and create an environment where students can explore their creativity freely through academic advice and mentoring. Ultimately, this can lead to a more enriching educational experience for students that contributes

to their overall development. In our educational system's current situation, many teachers are experiencing difficulties and facing complicated challenges because of their inadequate training in the field to which they belong. Since teachers are in demand and appraisal-focused, the fashion of teaching is very evident (Silvestre et al. 2020). Figure 4 shows how the MAPEH teachers manage creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development and the emergence of the three themes: Empowering Through Creative Engagement, Navigating Constraints to Foster Creative Empowerment, and Cultivating Creative Empowerment.

3.3. *Educational management insight is drawn from the study—*

The third objective of this study is to provide recommendations and best practices for MAPEH teachers and educational policymakers based on the study's findings. Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher, explore what educational insight and practices can be

3.3.1. Guiding principles for creative pedagogy—Based on the teacher's analyzed narration, explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study exploring practices for MAPEH teachers. The text says that using creative teaching methods in MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) education can help students succeed academically and develop as whole people. The study suggests that teachers should create personalized teaching strategies that fit each student's unique needs and interests. By doing this, students will be more engaged in their learning and have better outcomes overall. Moreover, this statement says that people who make decisions about education should think about giving teachers more help with teaching creativity and self-expression in a subject called MAPEH. The study found that it is essential for teachers to keep learning new ways of teaching creatively to do the best job possible. So, policymakers should give resources and support to training programs for MAPEH teachers to help them be better at their jobs. Teachers and policymakers need to understand the value of these aspects in education and work towards integrating them into policies and practices. It is important for teachers to receive continuous training and support to implement these practices in their classrooms effectively. The study also highlights the role of mindfulness in conflict resolution and classroom management. Based on the findings, policymakers should prioritize curriculum revisions that emphasize cross-disciplinary connections and real-world applications to enhance creative engage-

ment among students. This means educational policies should focus on connecting different subjects while emphasizing how they apply in real-life situations (Junio et al., Jonathan, 2019). This text emphasizes the importance of incorporating creativity, self-expression, mindfulness, cross-disciplinary connections, and real-world applications into MAPEH education policies to enhance student learning experiences. Teaching is a profession that many teachers enjoy doing because of their love and commitment to their sworn duty. On the other hand, some teachers, especially the new ones, experience high stress. After teaching, they leave the field of education due to a lack of administrative support, inability to manage personal and professional expectations, limited teaching resources, lack of professional development, and difficulty in handling behavioral problems in the classroom (Pestano Vargas. 2021).

Based on the analyzed narration of the teacher, explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study exploring practices for MAPEH teachers. As teachers, we must ensure our classrooms are welcoming and accepting of everyone. We should encourage students to try new things and take risks without fear of judgment or failure. Studies show that allowing students to think about how they come up with ideas and giving them feedback is crucial for their learning and progress. So let's create a safe space where creativity can flourish. As educators, we must prioritize creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment that encourages risk-taking and experimentation.

3.3.2. Policy Recommendations for Holistic Curriculum Integration.—

On the other hand, based on the interview data gathered from the teacher, explore what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study of exploring practices for MAPEH teachers and educational policymakers based on the findings of the study, considering the second theme, Policy Recommendations for Holistic Curriculum Integration. In analyzing the teacher's narration, explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study exploring practices for MAPEH teachers. The given text talks about the vital role that educational policymakers play in creating an environment that helps MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) teachers foster creativity and self-expression among students. This is crucial for enhancing their overall educational experience and personal development. Based on the findings, policymakers should prioritize funding research initiatives that explore practical strategies for fostering creativity and self-expression in MAPEH subjects, enabling evidence-based decision-making. Teachers should promote holistic curriculum integration in MAPEH subjects, while policymakers must support flexible scheduling and class structures for creative exploration and project-based learning. This text discusses how educational policymakers should provide enough resources and support to help teachers develop creative teaching methods in MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) classes. Based on research, the text suggests that the curriculum for these subjects should be changed to include creativity and self-expression as essential things for students to learn. This means that policymakers need to ensure that teachers can access materials like lesson plans or activities that encourage creativity in their classrooms. They also need professional development programs where they can learn new ways of teaching creatively. The goal is for students taking MAPEH classes to learn the basic concepts and express themselves through music, art, and physical movement. This requires a shift in how we teach these subjects so that children are engaged and interested while learning simultaneously. Likewise, suggests that policymakers should collaborate with various stakeholders, such as teachers, students, parents, and community members, to develop comprehensive approaches to promoting creativity and self-expression in MAPEH education. Doing so can create a supportive environment where students are encouraged to express themselves freely through music, arts, or physical activities (Hollow et al., 2019). In simpler terms, this means that policymakers have an important job of ensuring that schools provide opportunities for students to explore their creative side while also focusing on their health and well-being. They need to work closely with everyone involved in the education system to ensure enough resources are available to teach MAPEH subjects effectively. Ultimately, this will help students become more well-rounded individuals who are better prepared for life beyond school (Junio et al. 2019). Educational policymakers should involve MAPEH teachers in curriculum development to value their insights and expertise. Funding research initiatives to foster creativity and self-expression in MAPEH subjects is crucial for evidence-based decision-making. Offering a myriad of mechanisms to new teachers may help and support them to better assimilate into their new school cultures and roles. Implementing these mechanisms has proven to be a promising approach, significantly reducing the number of first-year teachers who experienced frustration, unrewarding, and intolerable difficulty throughout the school year and desired or decided to leave the profession (Hollow et al., 2019). Le Maistre Paré, (2018). The author suggests that policymakers (people who make rules for schools) should encourage teachers to be more creative in their teaching methods and assessments. This will help students learn better because they get different types of lessons from

different subjects working together. The idea is that when teachers work together across different subjects instead of just staying within their subject area, it creates a better student learning experience. It can be said that teaching has two faces: the experience that teaches how to learn and the experience that leads them to give up. In terms of learning, it can be said that one of the most important drivers for teachers to continue teaching is the students' achievements that they

themselves have been instruments in their success; if they are assigned to handle subjects, they are not specialized in most particularly teaching MAPEH components. Several novice teachers are at high rates. MAPEH teachers perceive their responsibilities in encouraging these time management qualities and the challenges they face in teachers' fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects (Stead, 2019).

3.3.3. Empowering teachers as agents of change—On the other hand, based on the interview data gathered from the teacher, explore what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study of exploring practices for MAPEH teachers and educational policy-makers based on the study's findings, considering the third theme empowering teachers as agents of change. Teachers can utilize these mechanisms as they begin their careers in education. The concern of the teachers assigned in different specializations about the lack of coping mechanisms is apparent in a specific subsection within the education field, specifically in geographical areas and subjects where these mechanisms are highly needed (Junio, Jacklyn Judith B. and Liwag; Jonathan, 2019). Based on the teacher's analyzed narration, it was observed that some of the topics or statements are about empowering MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) teachers to be innovators and change agents in their field. It emphasizes the importance of providing opportunities for professional growth so that these teachers can expand their skills and knowledge. Another statement was common statements about acknowledging and praising MAPEH teachers who show exceptional creativity and effectiveness in their teaching. MAPEH stands for Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health subjects taught in schools. This recognition aims to celebrate the hard work of these teachers who

go above and beyond to make learning fun, engaging, and effective for their students. Recognizing them through rewards or other forms of appreciation encourages them to continue doing a great job while inspiring others to do the same. It is like giving a pat on the back for a well-done job. Furthermore, another observed statement like talks about the significance of creating areas for MAPEH (Music et al. Education and Health) teachers to reflect and collaborate. These spaces help them share their best practices, think about their challenges in teaching these subjects, and exchange ideas. When such platforms are established, teachers can learn from one another's experiences and knowledge, which will ultimately lead to better education quality in the field of MAPEH. Moreover, the P.E. program aims to develop the physical prowess of the students, as well as their agility, endurance, vitality, and kinesthetic skills. Thus, P.E. is designed to help students mentally sound, physically strong, and emotionally balanced. Next, the Music program, on the other hand, is directed to expose students and pupils to the development of their appreciation for the culture and music of various regions worldwide. In addition, the program allows you to sing music from various genres, play different instruments, and listen to the recordings of various world artists. This program assists them in creating their music (Carreon, 2020). Supported by the idea of Lidser (2022), the statement from the narrative also talks about build-

ing collaborative learning communities among MAPEH educators by encouraging peer support and collaboration. This means that teachers should collaborate to share ideas and resources, ultimately benefiting their students. Overall, this text highlights the need for ongoing professional development among MAPEH educators to improve their students' education quality. By empowering these teachers with new skills and fostering a sense of community among them, we can create a better learning environment for everyone involved. This ultimately benefits students by providing more engaging and compelling learning experiences. For example, if a school strongly partners with its MAPEH teachers, educational policymakers, and community stakeholders, they might organize events that showcase student artwork or performances. These events could involve local artists or musicians from the community as well as parents of the students. Involving everyone in this way creates a sense of pride within the school community, which helps motivate students and educators alike. Bassar (2019) opined that sports and physical education should be a positive and constructive force in the growth and development of every child. Adequate time should be allotted to the growth and development of boys and girls during school days and periods when the children are not in school. Overall, by working together through partnerships like the one mentioned in the text above - schools can create better opportunities for their students while also strengthening ties with their communities. In the Philippines, under the K to 12 Curriculum, the Physical Education program seeks to provide opportunities for the physical development of Filipino learners through the development of various competencies under the primary education curriculum by providing appropriate activities and programs in the instruction (Montesur,2021). The Department of Education recognizes students' interest in disciplines such as Arts, Science, Language, and Sports. In its thrust to produce globally competitive learners, special curricular programs in secondary schools were implemented to meet the needs and talents of the students (DO 46 s. 2020). Furthermore, the needs and interests of the learners should be the prime consideration in creating and designing a curriculum (Hoyt-Oukada, 2023). Thus, students' needs, talents, and interests play a vital role and should be considered when implementing special curricular programs. The Department of Education offers special curricular programs in science and technology, journalism, foreign language, technical-vocational education, arts, and sports in secondary schools as part of the enhanced basic education curriculum (K12). The Deped should promote special curricular programs, especially the development of the sports program, in addition to primary education (Field, 2021). Figure 5 shows the educational management insight drawn from the study Teachers manage to handle creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development, and the emergence of the three themes are guiding principles for creative pedagogy, policy recommendations for holistic curriculum integration, and empowering teachers as agents of change.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in culturally responsive teachers through the lens of classroom advisers are also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—

Fig. 5. Educational management insights are drawn from the study

The study's findings are based on the data gathered from the target population, which consisted of twelve (12) participants from the lineup of public secondary school faculty. The findings disclosed that the first objective of this study was to examine the different practices based on their experience in fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects, to identify the teaching strategies and methods employed by MAPEH teachers to promote creativity and expression in their classrooms, and how do MAPEH teachers perceive the impact of creativity and self-expression on students' overall learning experience and personal development. To provide recommendations and best practices for MAPEH teachers and educational policymakers based on the study's findings. Finally, the study sought to draw educational insights from its findings considering the theme merged after saturation of the data gath-

4.2. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The teachers' lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression and the emergence of the three themes: adapting pedagogical approaches means pedagogy enables teachers to understand the best suitable practices for a classroom setting. It helps them to know how different students learn and grasp information so that they can tailor their lessons to satisfy those needs. It is likely to improve the quality of teaching and the way it is received by the students. , holistic approaches to learning, which focus on all aspects of an individual rather than just their academic or intellectual development. One of the fundamental key principles of Holistic Education presents learning as something that should be relevant and meaningful to MAPEH students and diverse Strategies for teaching a diverse mix of learners; it might consider small groups of similar interests, learning styles, or even mixed

ered, such as adapting pedagogical approaches to cultivate individuality, holistic approaches, and diverse strategies, empowering through creative engagement, navigating constraints to foster creative empowerment, cultivate creative empowerment guiding principles for creative pedagogy, policy recommendations for holistic curriculum integration, empowering teachers as agents of change. Fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects: teachers practice in focus. Fostering creativity and expression in MAPEH subjects requires a holistic approach that involves collaboration among educators, policymakers, parents, and communities. By recognizing the implications of research findings, stakeholders can work together to create learning environments that empower students to explore their creative potential and express themselves authentically in the context of MAPEH education.

groupings of abilities. Studies show that peer teaching can be an extremely effective strategy, encouraging independence and strengthening social relationships. The MAPEH teachers manage creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development and the emergence of the three themes: empowering through creative engagement, navigating constraints to foster creative empowerment, and cultivating creative empowerment. The research highlights the study's implications about exploring the role of MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects. The study highlights the need for a paradigm shift in MAPEH education towards pedagogical practices prioritizing creativity and expression. This implied a departure from traditional instructional methods towards more innovative, student-centered approaches that cultivate creativity and self-expression. Educators require tailored professional development programs to enhance their capacity to

foster creativity and expression effectively in MAPEH subjects. This suggests the need for ongoing training, workshops, and collaborative learning opportunities to equip teachers with the necessary skills and strategies. The educational management insight drawn from the study is that teachers manage to handle creativity and self-expression in students' overall learning experience and personal development. This leads to the emergence of three themes: guiding principles for creative pedagogy were teaching along the idea of creative pedagogy, which means that we teach a field of knowledge by successively extending a given semiotic context around a critical concept, learning then means creating a solution following our six-element process of creativity. policy recommendations for holistic curriculum integration was a recommendation to higher authority for the development of the program that would focus on the whole child, encouraging the development of their physical, social, emotional, and intellectual needs. Holistic education helps create a positive learning environment where children can

develop the skills, knowledge, and values that would serve them for a lifetime, and empowerment of teachers as agents of change was important to note when considering the roles of teachers as agents of change, for not only do they need to have increased knowledge and understanding of global issues and the skills to impart that knowledge, they also need to be empathetic to concerns of social justice and recognize that learning can influence for changes or rebranding the old form of system. Curriculum reform is clearly needed to integrate creativity and expression more comprehensively into MAPEH subjects. This includes revising curriculum frameworks to incorporate creative activities, interdisciplinary connections, and opportunities for self-expression that align with educational goals and standards. Educational institutions and policymakers must allocate resources to support creative initiatives in MAPEH education. This includes providing access to arts materials, sports equipment, technological tools, and other resources that facilitate creative exploration and expression in the classroom.

4.3. Future Directions—The Future directions stem from a study exploring the role of fostering creativity and expression in handling MAPEH subjects, with a specific focus on teachers' practices. The study suggests the need for innovative assessment methods to accurately measure students' creative abilities and self-expression in MAPEH subjects. This implied moving beyond traditional assessment forms towards performance-based tasks, portfolios, and authentic assessments that capture the multifaceted nature of creativity and expression. Overall, the study underscores the importance of fostering creativity and expression in MAPEH subjects and highlights the various implications for teacher practice, curriculum development, resource allocation, assessment strategies, inclusive education, and com-

munity engagement. By addressing these implications, stakeholders can work towards creating vibrant learning environments that empower students to explore their creative potential and express themselves authentically in the context of MAPEH education. This study was equally significant to the school heads. It was a good reference for them to examine the MAPEH subjects, ultimately enriching students' learning experiences, personal development, and future success. It was also significant to the policymakers for planning and drafting future training and seminars for teachers to properly address implementation gaps in utilizing the roles and responsibilities of principals in the teaching and learning process. Finally, it was significant to fellow researchers who wanted to conduct a similar or comparative study. This study was

significant to teachers. In it, teachers revealed their actual lived experiences in implementing management approaches to the subject in school development, especially in this new standard setting. They may also adopt the teachers' coping practices regarding their challenges. The study of the teachers' lived experience shared by MAPEH teachers in fostering creativity and self-expression is an evolving field with potential future directions. Some possible future directions for research in this area include: Comparative Studies: Comparative studies across different educational contexts, such as different countries or school systems, can shed light on how cul-

tural, social, and contextual factors influence the experiences of MAPEH subjects, ultimately enriching students' learning experiences, personal development, and future success. Comparisons can provide valuable insights into the transferability of practices and strategies across different settings. By pursuing these future directions, educators, researchers, policymakers, and community stakeholders may collectively advance the role of fostering creativity and expression in MAPEH subjects, ultimately enriching students' learning experiences, personal development, and future success.

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